

AN UNDERSTANDING OF THE CAPABILITIES OF THE CAMTASIA STUDIO SOFTWARE TOOL.

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Abstract: The article provides extensive and understandable information about the Camtasia program and its capabilities, how to record videos using the program.

Keywords: Camtasia Studio, video, program, interface, desktop, control panel, audio recording.

Camtasia Studio is designed for creating video tutorials, presentations, and other similar materials that are shown to viewers. In addition to video recording, Camtasia Studio also has the ability to edit video. Using the Camtasia Studio program, you can easily record all the processes that are happening on the computer monitor.

It is possible to record the whole area of the monitor screen or a separate area of it, after which we will be able to give different video and audio effects. If you choose a computer with high enough performance to record the processes observed on the monitor screen, productivity will definitely increase. Another advantage of Camtasia Studio is that it has its own TechSmit Screen Capture Codec, which gives better results when encoding images. Its algorithm minimizes overloads on the system, so this program can be used even on computers with low performance.

1. The main features of the program:
2. Processes monitored on the monitor screen and through web cameras,
3. High-quality recording of sound from the microphone.
4. Giving different visual effects to videos.
5. Cut, merge, delete and add video tracks.
6. Record and edit audio.
7. Save the video in formats convenient for us: SWF, FLV, AVI, MOV, WMV, PPT, GIF, RM, CAMV.

The number of programs designed to capture video images is increasing day by day. This is due to the increase and popularity of video courses and video lessons on the Internet. The Camtasia Studio program differs from others in that it captures video images in high quality.

The program records everything that happens on the desktop, including the movement of the cursor (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Program interface.

1. Desktop; 2. Control panel; 3. Time scale; 4. Proigryvatyel;

Camtasia Studio includes four utilities: Camtasia Recorder, Camtasia Theater, Camtasia Player, Camtasia MenuMaker. Camtasia Studio videos work perfectly on YouTube-type sites, on iPhone devices, as well as in any programs designed to view video on ordinary personal computers, and we can find many media files on the Internet that teach how to work in a specific software environment. At the same time, the program allows you to save the image quality without any loss and save the video in a minimal size.

The working principle of Camtasia Studio

Figure 2.

This program not only captures the screen in high quality, but also allows you to edit it in a very simple and understandable way. It's so simple and easy to understand that you don't need any experience or training to use it. In fact, the program has a lot of possibilities, but I will talk step by step about the possibilities that you will need to prepare a video lesson on programming.

After installing the program, if you open it, the following window will appear:

Figure 3. The working window of the program.

From there, if you click on one of the buttons in the red frame, the window will be temporarily closed and a new window will appear in the lower right corner of your screen as follows 2. You can create an e-learning course in Camtasia Studio.

As soon as you press the red –rec button on it, press F10 to stop recording will appear on the screen, then the numbers 3,2,1 will be written and the recording will start.

During the recording, go through your lesson according to the plan and explain it (also check that your microphone is in the correct position on the computer). When you are recording, press F10 to stop. After that, the program will immediately open the result of your recording in its player. Click the "Save and Edit" button on the edge and save it with a name.

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